

THE DEVELOPMENT AND USES OF GLASS/CARBON HYBRIDS

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INTRODUCTION

A hybrid composite may be defined as one which contains two or more reinforcing fibres and the object is to produce structures which hopefully combine the desirable properties of both reinforcements.

It will be clear that in theory such hybrids comprise a large class but in practice the choice narrows down to a small number of pairs and a smaller number of triads.

The main presentation in this paper deals with composites containing both glass and carbon fibre, the latter and more expensive material providing a substantial improvement in stiffness to the cheaper, more familiar glass.

It has long be realized that although glass-reinforced plastics are strong they are lacking in rigidity, and many procedures have evolved to compensate for this such as local thickening, double curvatures, integral ribs and sandwich constructions.

In looking to glass/carbon hybrids as a new approach to the problem of stiffness two questions arise:-

"Does one in practice get the static properties one might reasonably expect?" and "Are there any hidden technical penalties which could arise either in the short-term or the long-term from such a mixing process?"

HISTORICAL

Looking back over the past decade, we can distinguish two successive phases of interest and development. In 1967 the earliest glass/carbon hybrids were made using the batch form of carbon, i.e. 10,000 filament tows about one metre in length. Bundles of these tows were built into the walls of typical glass-fibre lay-ups at intervals of 1-15 cm so as to form slightly raised ribs. At the same time the lay-up itself was made lighter and thinner by omitting one or more layers of glass.

This method of construction was applied to racing cars with immediate

success, notably the GT40 Ford which won the 1968 and 1969 Le Mans 24-hour race.

Car designers were enthusiastic and hybrid bodies are now the accepted norm for racing cars.

The next commercial application was to canoes and kayaks (1968 onwards) where the combination of greater hull stiffness and substantial weight savings led to many victories over traditional all-glass craft.

Similar novel ideas in the use of batch fibre were made by Wells and Hancox who placed layers or rods of cured CFRP within GRP panels to improve their bending stiffness. Dukes and Griffiths produced home-made layers of carbon fibre/polyester resin pre-preg which were then incorporated into GRP laminates.

All the above were straightforward trial-and-error exercises, the static stiffnesses being improved and verified by laboratory tests while practical experience confirmed the robustness of the design.

This is the so-called "empirical" phase, the success of which led to a more thoughtful and rigorous approach toward hybrids in general. In the "scientific" phase these began a systematic assessment of static and dynamic properties, requiring a standard range of unidirectional hybrids in which the glass/carbon ratio could be varied within wide limits.

At this point, 1970 onwards, continuous carbon fibre became available and a weaving programme was put in hand.

Particular difficulties arise in the weaving of hybrids. The type and amount of size must be suitable, not only for the weaving itself but also for the subsequent impregnation with laminating resin.

Carbon and glass fibres stretch and relax to a different extent to that a close matching of tow diameters and a fine adjustment of the warp tensions are required.

From this research has come a wide variety of all-carbon and hybrid constructions including the unidirectional series mentioned above.

All these products are commercially available from our weavers, Carr Reinforcements Ltd.

THE MAIN TECHNICAL POINTS

It is possible to identify four basic types of hybrid which differ in the subdivision of the reinforcing phases and their geometrical arrangement.

The simplest type is the insert, already mentioned in the empirical stage, which involves sizeable bundles or rods of carbon with a cross-section measuring some millimetres each way (Fig.1a). The introduction of pultruded profiles based on continuous fibre has considerably increased the scope for this type of hybrid.

In the second or layer type (Fig.1b) both reinforcements are present as separate laminations of roughly equal thickness, usually less than one millimetre. The layers are stacked in an optimum sequence with carbon towards the outside of a beam, though not always outermost since glass is used as a protective layer in some applications.

TABLE 1

Mechanical properties glass/carbon hybrids (Matrix resin-vinyl ester)

Warp Construction	V_f carbon at 60% total fibre content	Flexural strength MPa	Flexural modulus GPa	Interlaminar shear strength MPa	Tensile strength MPa	Tensile modulus GPa
All-glass	0.0	844	34.6	40	780	39.9
4:1	0.13	773	46.9	43	660	56.0
3:1	0.16	843	50.6	42	686	60.2
2:1	0.21	943	59.0	43	715	65.2
1:1	0.31	953	69.3	40	749	74.6
All-carbon	0.6	1240	101.2	38	1132	115.1

Classification of Hybrids

Fig. 1

The next stage of sub-division gives rise to the uniform type, wherein both reinforcing fibres are present within each layer as a repeating pattern of tows. The structure consists of a number of such identical layers bonded together (Fig. 1c).

Finally, there is the sandwich type in which thin skins of hybrid are bonded to sheets of honeycomb, plywood or expanded plastics. Where plywood is used as a sandwich core material, the hybrid is a triad comprising cellulose, glass and carbon fibre (Fig. 1d).

PROPERTIES

For intelligent design, one needs to know the strengths and stiffnesses of a number of hybrids of different glass/carbon ratios, and it would be useful if we could predict hybrid properties from those of the constituent fibres.

Both the insert and layer types of hybrid have large local concentrations of carbon and to avoid possible complications the uniform type was chosen for the following investigation.

A series of unidirectional fabrics was woven using a standard 5000 filament carbon warp and a standard 600 tex glass warp differing only in the ratio of each. Similar all-glass and all-carbon cloths were used as the controls.

The results are summarized in Table I and are shown graphically in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, which give plots of stiffness and strength respectively against composition.

CARBON/GLASS HYBRID - PLOT OF TENSILE MODULUS AGAINST COMPOSITION

Fig. 2

CARBON/GLASS HYBRID - PLOT OF TENSILE STRENGTH AGAINST COMPOSITION

Fig. 3

Fig. 2 gives rise to little comment, since modulus rises smoothly with increased carbon content and the simple Mixture Law is sufficient for most calculations.

Fig. 3 is more interesting.

With the addition of a small amount of carbon fibre the tensile strength falls. This is in line with the usual prediction that a few filler particles act as a stress concentration. The strength soon rises and for the useful range of carbon/glass ratios remains above the line GAC.

This is evidence for a load-sharing theory rather than the alternative mechanism which says that the carbon fibre in a hybrid - being much stiffer - will take all the applied load.

Furthermore, at carbon failure this load would be transferred suddenly to the glass causing it to fail catastrophically.

The actual behaviour, and further evidence for load-sharing, is seen in the stress/strain diagram for a typical 3:1 glass/carbon hybrid (Fig. 4).

From the plot three things are evident:-

- i. The straight-line portion of the curve rises well past the point at which the carbon should fail if it were taking all the load.
- ii. The straight line portion rises somewhat beyond the point where carbon would fail at the normal failing strain for CFRP. In other words failure is delayed and we see the famous "hybrid effect" of Hayashi.
- iii. Even when failure has occurred, the load does not fall at once to zero, as in CFRP. Rather the load stays relatively high, rising and falling only a little, as it transfers from carbon to glass. It should be noticed that because of this transition the area under the stress/strain curve is much greater than for monolithic CFRP.

HYBRID STRESS / STRAIN CURVE WEAVING RATIO OF
3 WARPS GLASS TO 1 WARP CARBON

Fig. 4

Exactly similar behaviour was reported by Marshall who examined the same hybrids in the flexural mode.

How are the benefits of the hybrid effect to explained?

We have examined hybrids holographically under tensile stress and seen no evidence of a differential strain between the two types of fibre.

Neither is it logical to accept that all the carbon fibres have suddenly undergone a magical increase in total extensibility. Rather we must look to the statistical nature of failure in fibrous composites which has two aspects:-

a. Fibre Bundle Theory

This states that the weakest carbon fibres and the weakest tows are the first to fail at the normal strain; but they are firmly stuck to and surrounded by a strong fibre-reinforced matrix of GRP. Although the carbon fibres are now discontinuous they continue to share load and to contribute to laminate stiffness.

The remaining unbroken carbon fibres are stronger and at the same stiffness fail at a higher breaking strain than the value for bulk CFRP.

This discussion, which is a general argument on the relative roles of low-extension and high-extension fibres, has been amplified by Zweben in an elegant paper on carbon/Kevlar hybrids where carbon is the low-extension reinforcement. It is reminiscent of the Darwinian theory of survival of the fittest.

b. Crack Propagation Theory

The tensile failure of a well-bonded carbon fibre laminate is a sudden event with the crack propagating very rapidly across the width of the specimen.

On the other hand, the characteristic failure in GRP - the fibrous shaving brush appearance - denotes an excellent crack-stopper.

Thus a high proportion of glass in a hybrid will markedly reduce the chances of catastrophic crack propagation.

Zweiben has called this phenomenon "suppression" and we can combine both of the above strands of thought in a broad statement that "In a hybrid, suppression leads to the survival of the strongest members of the low-extension tribe."

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR - RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

There is little doubt that engineers have been very worried about the possible fatigue life of hybrids supposing that the moderate performance of GRP would be reduced still further by the broken ends of carbon-fibre in a hybrid acting as stress-raisers.

In practice the behaviour is quite different.

The fatigue tests were carried out at a frequency of 10 Hz in fluctuating tension on the range of hybrids already tested statically. Again an all-glass laminate of similar construction was used as the control.

The family of S-N curves are given in Fig. 5 and it will be seen that the fatigue life of the hybrids is better than that of the control by a considerable margin. Moreover the fatigue life improves as the carbon fibre content increases. For example, at a stress of 300 MPa, which is somewhat under half of ultimate, the all-glass laminate failed at about 2×10^4 cycles of stress whereas the 3:1 hybrid had a life of 3×10^6 cycles, over one hundred times better.

We can tackle the prediction of fatigue behaviour in hybrids by the following analysis:-

The cross-section through a hybrid specimen has the appearance of a mosaic, consisting of a number of small areas of CRFP, each having the same V_f as the hybrid overall, which are mixed with small areas of GRP to the

S - N DIAGRAM FOR GLASS AND HYBRID COMPOSITES

Fig. 5

same V_f . Suppose these small areas were gathered together their sums would be:-

A_c = area fraction of the carbon-phase (total area fraction of CFRP).

A_g = area fraction of the glass-phase (total area fraction of GRP).

Assuming the load on the hybrid is shared, with both phases straining together, the stresses in each phase are as follows:-

$$\epsilon = \frac{\sigma_c}{E_c} = \frac{\sigma_g}{E_g} = \frac{\sigma_{hyb}}{E_{hyb}}$$

where E_{hyb} = modulus of the hybrid.

E_c = modulus of the carbon-phase.

E_g = modulus of the glass-phase.

σ_{hyb} = nominal average stress over the hybrid cross-section

while σ_c and σ_g are stresses in the carbon-phase and glass-phase respectively.

But $E_{hyb} = E_g A_g + E_c A_c$.

$$\text{Whence } \sigma_g = \frac{E_g \sigma_{hyb}}{E_{hyb}} = \frac{E_g \sigma_{hyb}}{E_g A_g + E_c A_c} = \sigma_{hyb} \left[A_g + \frac{A_c E_c}{E_g} \right]^{-1}$$

$$\text{Similarly } \sigma_c = \frac{E_c \sigma_{hyb}}{E_{hyb}} = \frac{E_c \sigma_{hyb}}{E_g A_g + E_c A_c} = \sigma_{hyb} \left[A_c + \frac{A_g E_g}{E_c} \right]^{-1}$$

Inspection of the last two equations shows that if any phase is made stiffer i.e. it has a greater modulus, then the stress in that phase will increase. However, if the amount of the stiffer phase increases relative to the other, in other words if the area fraction gets bigger, then the stresses in both phases will be lowered.

The general conclusion - and the prediction - is that if the stiffer fibre has a better resistance to fatigue than its partner an increase in area fraction will improve the fatigue life of the hybrid. This is exactly what happens with carbon and glass.

There is a further point. We know the CFRP has a virtually flat S-N curve. Above it fatigue failure may occur at any time and we introduce the idea of a threshold or fatigue-critical stress below which fatigue failures rarely occur.

On the other hand GRP has a definite downward S-N curve, so that endurance is fairly predictable if the stress is known. Unfortunately the fatigue limit is a small fraction of the ultimate monotonic (single loading) stress.

Therefore we can distinguish two very different stress conditions in such a hybrid:-

In the first and exceptionally, we are above the fatigue-critical stress

for the carbon fibre phase and there may be early fatigue failure of the carbon leading to early failure of the glass. This is poor design since phase stresses can be readily calculated from the equations given above.

In the second and normally, we are below the fatigue-critical stress for the carbon phase and the life of the hybrid will be better than that of GRP carrying the same load because the stress in the glass-phase will be lower.

To give a relevant example, in the hybrid series considered here the fatigue-critical stress for carbon is about 900 MPa.

Theoretical and experimental values are given for boundary fatigue stresses in the hybrid, i.e. nominal stresses in the hybrid at which the stress in the carbon-phase reaches 900 MPa.

<u>Glass/Carbon</u> <u>Ratio</u>	<u>Boundary Fatigue Stresses (MPa)</u>	
	<u>Calculated</u>	<u>Experimental</u>
4:1	566	560
3:1	583	620
2:1	621	645

FABRICATION

The opinion is generally held that carbon fibre composites are more difficult to fabricate than glass.

This belief arises because the common form of carbon is the unwoven unidirectional prepreg whilst glass is available to the fabricator in many convenient forms. The difference shows up clearly in creating surfaces of double curvature where the tailoring of glass mat or fabric is well-known.

It is true - but not widely appreciated - that woven glass/carbon hybrids can be handled just as readily as the all-glass materials.

Hybrid fabrics pass through the dipping or coating machines just like the glass ones and make high-quality prepregs with phenolic and epoxy resins. Moreover with liquid resins such as epoxy and polyester the wetting-out of hybrid fabrics is assisted by the resin size which is necessarily applied for weaving. Clearing of the glass strands, which signifies saturation of the tows, also acts as a tell-tale for the carbon.

Although press and autoclave moulding are common for hybrid pre-pregs there is a growing tendency towards the wet lay-up vacuum-bag procedures that are common for glass.

A great point is scored if the curing process can be speeded up with gentle heat and the RAE vacuum-box is a typical unit of this type. The mould surface is an electrical hot-plate comprising a layer of carbon-fibre cloth acting as the resistance, bonded between insulating layers of glass.

Sandwich constructions are readily made either by co-curing or by separately bonding cured skins to cores. Fig. 6 shows a selection of flat, single and double curvature specimens.

Fig. 6

ECONOMICS

Initial experiments with woven hybrids were done with a shuttle loom operating at about 90 picks per minute. While this was perfectly adequate for woven tape or cloth up to 160 mm wide it was unsatisfactory for broad goods since the small weft capacity meant frequent stoppages and unsightly splicing knots.

Subsequent development work concentrated on the rapier loom which does away with the shuttle and produces weft by drawing tow from a large package across the warp threads. The weft is cut automatically after each return stroke.

Rapier looms can run at 300 picks per minute or more and the combination of higher speed and wider cloth as compared with the shuttle loom, gives a big reduction in the weaving cost per unit area.

Another feature of the rapier is the ability to weave extra selvages at convenient stations across the loom for example the mid-point. Subsequent splitting yields convenient half-sidith fabrics, etc.

Comparative costs were calculated for a series of composites comprising 50% by weight vinyl ester matrix and 50% of woven cloth reinforcement. The cloth varied from all-carbon, through hybrids of different glass/carbon ratio, to all-glass construction.

The table below gives mean costs per kilo together with basic raw material costs and it should be noted that resin and glass prices are fairly stable while those for carbon fibre and for weaving can be further reduced as the scale of operation is increased.

TABLE 2
Comparative costs for woven hybrids

Composition	Mean cost per kilo
All-glass	£ 8.00
4:1 glass/carbon	£13.70
3:1 glass/carbon	£15.12
2:1 glass/carbon	£17.50
1:1 glass/carbon	£22.50
Carbon	£36.50
Assumptions	
Carbon fibre	£60 per kilo
Glass fibre	£ 3 per kilo
Vinyl ester resin	£ 3 per kilo
Weaving charge	£10 per kilo

It will be seen that hybrids give the designer the ability to add extra stiffness and fatigue resistance to a component without adding to the weight but simply adding to the expense; and it is the task of the development man to identify and exploit those areas where such weight-saving and efficiency can be charged for.

APPLICATIONS

Sports

One of the most promising areas is in sports equipment and items such as fishing-rods, archery bows, clubs and racquets of all sorts are well known.

Hybrid-bodied racing cars have already been mentioned and are an important test-bed which could introduce items to the mass-production end of the automobile and truck industries.

The immediate success of the RAE work on canoes and kayaks led us to consider the more complex problem of racing sculls.

The modern rowing machine is a superb example of the traditional wood-working art which has hitherto resisted all the efforts of glass-fibre laminators to compete. True they make robust glass-fibre tubs which are much heavier and are used for training purposes, but all serious racing is done in wooden hulls.

A single-seater hybrid was constructed and tested thoroughly. It soon became clear that although this outperformed the wooden hull handsomely it was by no means the entire story. As the weight of the hull was reduced the weight of other components, particularly the riggers, became a significant part of the whole and further design exercises became necessary.

The present design of the machines now made commercially at Carbocraft Ltd., East Molesley, comprise a carbon/glass layer hybrid skin with an aluminum honeycomb or Rohacell core to the sandwich.

Fig. 7

Sandwich construction is used not only for the hull, ribs, stateroom, floor and sax-boards; a radical departure was to make the canvases (topside of the hull beyond both ends of the stateroom) as a lightweight sandwich bonded into the gunwale of the hull to complete the section and give it extra rigidity. A Carbocraft eight, selling for about £3,600 is stronger, stiffer and lighter than the traditional wooden boat costing about £6,000.

Model-making

Another application for hybrids is in model-making, particularly working scale models. As the thickness of skin-cladding and other members is reduced, one is hopelessly lacking in rigidity. Fig. 7 shows a 3:1 plain weave hybrid being used for a model helicopter fuselage.

In the non-scale flying area hybrids are being considered for the larger models of powered machines and radio-controlled gliders particularly for the wings.

Aerospace

There are a number of secondary structures such as fairings, flaps, luggage-racks, doors, bulk-heads and air-ducts (most of which are stiffness designed) which look promising for hybrids. Helicopters are a fruitful area because of the importance of minimum weight.

The helicopter blade is receiving a lot of attention because the inclusion of bias fibres in carbon puts up the torsional stiffness while their longitudinal stiffness remains similar to that of the 0° glass fibres in the

spar. Fuselage panels in hybrid will probably be designed as sandwiches to replace single-skin light alloy construction.

Civil Engineering

Conventional GRP has a good reputation as a shell for casting concrete, the surface giving a long-life and trouble-free parting. However such form-work often lacks rigidity and the more enterprising contractors are starting to look at the possibilities of hybrids. In a similar way, plywood is a very popular material for form-work panelling and the strength and stiffness of ply are considerably improved by a single layer of hybrid bonded to each side. The table below gives results for typical 9 mm ply.

TABLE 3
Flexural tests on plywood and carbon/glass/plywood hybrid

Materials	Ultimate Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)
9 mm ply	Mean = 84.0 = 12,180 lbf/in ²	Mean = 10.1 = 1.5 x 10 ⁶ lbf/in ²
3:1 glass carbon cloth on 9 mm ply	Mean = 128 = 18,560 lbf/in ²	Mean = 14.5 = 2.15 x 10 ⁶ lbf/in ²

There has been an increase in mean strength of 52.5% and an increase in stiffness of 43.5%.

Another application is in folded plate designs where the ease of fabrication of GRP is attractive but the low modulus leads to excessive deflections and premature failure. It was shown, together with the Civil Engineering Department of Surrey University, that reinforcement of the corner angles with carbon fibre stabilized the plate. Simple pultruded rods of triangular section were bonded into the GRP to form an insert hybrid.

A somewhat related application has been found in chemical storage vessels often made in a chopped strand/polyester construction. As the size of these tanks has increased bulging of the sides when fully laden becomes very pronounced. A layer of hybrid cloth on the outsides of the GRP, or a suitable array of unidirectional bands has solved the problem in a simple manner.

The Arts

Mechanical properties apart, there is no doubt that some hybrids look most attractive and the possibilities are becoming known to artists, craftsmen and architects.

At the London College of Furniture the design and construction of hybrid chairs is already under way as a student exercise and there may be further applications in the construction of musical instruments such as guitars and violins.

Screens, room-dividers, built-in furniture, temporary and pre-fabricated buildings are other possible outlets.

Fig. 8

Medical

There is a continuing need for splints, supports, artificial legs and other devices for the physically handicapped and bioengineers are always on the alert for more efficient materials to replace the traditional (and rather Victorian) steel and leather.

Fig. 8 shows an experimental knee-ankle-foot orthosis weighing 127 grams. The $\pm 45^\circ$ orientation to give torsional stiffness can be clearly seen. The design is difficult in that the lower end fits within the shoe. The ankle section must be thin and allow for considerable deflection at each stride. Whereas the all-glass prototype failed prematurely in fatigue the hybrid is satisfactory.

CONCLUSIONS

What lessons are to be learned from our experience with glass/carbon hybrids over the past five years?

The theoretical difficulties have been resolved and the load-sharing principle is accepted. Woven hybrids are easily produced and can be fabricated by the same techniques that are well established for glass.

By exploiting the greater stiffness and fatigue resistance in the hybrids, new applications have been identified where conventional GFP would find it hard to follow.

Even if this new business were only 1/20th the size of present GRP market it would be a useful growth area for the fabricator. It also represents an enormous percentage increase in the potential demand for carbon fibre.

SESSION 20: PANEL DISCUSSION
THE TEACHING OF COMPOSITE TECHNOLOGIES

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No notes were taken.

SESSION 21:
AEROSPACE APPLICATION OF
ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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